

Devyāmata, sūtrapāṭalakṣaṇaēkāśītipāṭalaḥ, edition.

N f 83v line 5; M f54v, line 5; W f60r, line 5

81.1 ataḥ parivīśeṣeṇa vāstuyāgaṃ suniścitam
sūtrapāṭaṃ krameṇaiva procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

81.2 śuklapakṣe sunakṣatre sutithau cottarāyaṇe
sugṛhe sunimitte ca sarvasambhārasambhṛtaḥ

Nf84r

Wf60v

81.3 śaṅkhavāditranirghoṣair vedamaṅgalasusvanaiḥ
ācāryaḥ sthapatir vāpi prāsādaṃ sūtrayet kramāt

81.4 āhrtya sarvasambhāraṃ śāstrajñō nipunaḥ śuciḥ
kṛtvā tu susamā bhūmiḥ prāsadamaṇḍapāyatam

Mf55r

81.5 jagatiprāntavistīrṇaṃ nimnonnatavivarjitam
pūrvadiksādhanam kṛtvā gomayenopalepayet

81.6 kṛtvā surakṣitam vidvān sarvato nirupadravam
susnātācamya vidhinā śuklavāso jitendriyaḥ

81.7 pāḍau prakṣālya cācamya vāstubhūmiviśeṣataḥ
kīlakāsūtram āhrtya sūtrayet susahāyavān

Ω = NM(→W)

N lacks 3abc due to folio damage.

1c pāṭam] N; pātraṃ M

3a nighoṣair] em.; nighoṣai M

3c ācāryaḥ] em.; ācārya M • sthapatir] em.; sthapati M

3d prāsādaṃ] em.; prāsāda M

4b śuciḥ] em.; śuci NM

4c kṛtvā tu susamā bhūmiḥ] em.; kṛtvātusamābhūmi M; kṛtvā[***]bhūmi N

5a vistīrṇaṃ] em.; vistīrṇa NM

6a vidvān] N; vidvā M

6d vāso] em.; vāsā NM

7d susahāyavān] N; susakhāyavān M

- 81.8 maṅgalaṃ kalaśaṃ śubhraṃ toyapūrṇaṃ navaṃ dṛḍham
praśastapallavopetaṃ candanena sucarcitam
- 81.9 vedavāditranirghoṣair mantravit susamāhitaḥ
sthāpayen maṅgalārthaṃ tu udagīśānagocare
- 81.10 paraśumaṣṭilāsūtraṃ kīlakālakṣaṇānvitam
kalaśasyottare bhāge saṃsthāpya tatra sthāpayet
- 81.11 gandhapuṣpādibhiḥ samyak pūjayed viśvakarmaṇam
tataḥ sampūjayet mantri paraśvādīn kīlaṃ kramāt Wf61r
- 81.12 sampūjya vidhivat sarvān praṇamya viśvakarmaṇam
vijñāpya gṛhayet prāṇmukhaḥ sūtram ārabhet
- 81.13 pūrvadīksādhanam proktaṃ dīksūtraṃ dvigataṃ tathā
kṛtvā sūtrasamāṃ bhūmiṃ prāsādam sūtrayet tataḥ M55v

Ω = NM(→W)

8b pūrṇam] N; pūrṇa M • navaṃ] N; nava M

9a vādītra] N; nādītra M

10a maṣṭilā] N; muṣṭilā M

10b lakṣaṇānvitam] N; lakṣaṇānvitāḥ M

10c kalaśasyottare] N; kalasasyottar[[o]]e M

11a puṣpādibhiḥ] N; puṣpādibhis M

11b viśva] N; iśva M

11c tataḥ] M; tatas N

11d paraśvādīn] em.; paraśvādīn N; paraśvād[[i]]īn M • kīlaṃ] N; kila M

13b dīksūtraṃ] em.; dīksūtra M; dvīksūtraṃ N

13c bhūmiṃ] N; bhūmi M

- 81.14 prāsādaṃ pṛṣṭhataḥ sūtraṃ saṃsthāpya jagater bahiḥ
tāvat prāsārayet sūtraṃ yāvat syād aṅganāntarām
- 81.15 tataḥ sutānitaṃ kṛtvā ubhayamatsyamadhyagam
sūtraṃ sampātayed yatnāt sūtramārgaṃ ca lāñchayet
- 81.16 tathā ca pārśvayor madhye yāvat syāj jagater bahiḥ
āsphālya matsyayor madhye prāsādaṃ sūtrayet tataḥ
- 81.17 prākpraticīgataṃ sūtraṃ yāmyodīcīgataṃ ca yat
mūlasūtraṃ tu taṃ vidyāj jīvasūtraṃ tu madhyagam
- 81.18 mūlasūtraṃ dhruvaṃ kṛtvā prāsādaṃ sūtrayet tataḥ
yāvaddhastair abhipretaṃ tāvadbhiḥ parikalpayet

$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$

- 15c sampātayed yatnāt ; saṃpātadyatnāt N; sāṃpālayedyatnā M
16a pārśvayor madhye] em.; pārśvayomadhye M; pārśvayodhye N
17c vidyāj] N; viṃdyā M
18a sūtraṃ] N; sūtra M
18c abhipretaṃ] N; abhipreta M
18d tāvadbhiḥ] N; tāvadbhi M

81.19 jagādis tu vibhāgaṃ tu saṃkalpya sarvato bahiḥ
bhājayen mūlasūtreṇa garbhaprāgrīvamaṇḍapān

81.20 paridhiṃ sādhayet teṣāṃ caturdikṣu pṛthak pṛthak
vidikṣu karṇasūtreṇa karṇān teṣāṃ prasārayet

Wf61v

81.21 āyāmaṃ vistaraṃ samyak jñātvā teṣāṃ vicakṣaṇaḥ
madhyasūtrānusāreṇa prāsādaṃ parikalpayet

Nf84v

81.22 yāvad dhastair abhipretaṃ prāsādaṃ parikalpayet
jīvasūtraṃ caturdikṣu tasyaivārdhena lāñchayet

Ω = NM(→W)

19c sūtreṇa] em.; mantreṇa NM

19d prāgrīva] N; prāgīva M

20d karṇān] N; karṇa M

22b parikalpayet] N; vistareṇatu M

- 81.23 madhyasūtrabahir madhyāt tena mānena mānavit
vidikṣu sādhyet karṇān prāsādasya susaṃmitān
- 81.24 evaṃ susaṃmitaṃ kṛtvā prāsādaṃ paridhisamam Mf56r
śaṅkūni veśayet tatra vidikṣu mastake kramāt
- 81.25 tataḥ praṇamya vijñāpya kumbhasthaṃ viśvakarmaṇam
kīlakāṃ maṣṭilāṃ caiva paraśuṃ ca samāharet
- 81.26 sitacandanaliptāṅgān śuklapuṣpasubhūṣitān
ālaṃkṛtān vitān gr̥hya trisūtrapariveṣṭitam
- 81.27 madhusarpidadhukṣīraḥśaṅkumūlaṃ pralepayet
śaṅkuṃ saṃgr̥hya yatnena paraśumaṣṭilāṃ tataḥ
- 81.28 ūṃkārasvastipuṇyāhair gītavāditraniśvanaiḥ
gatvā dakṣiṇe pūrveṇa sarvasambhārasambhṛtaḥ Wf62r
- 81.29 tasminn āsanam ādāya śuklavastraparicchadam
prāṇmukhasthapatir dhīra upaviśyaṃ tu śāstravit
- 81.30 śaṅkuṃ dakṣiṇahastena gr̥hya vāmena tat punaḥ
bhūmyāṃ saṃsthāpya yatnena samyag mudrām udāharet

Ω = NM(→W)

23d susaṃmitān] N; [[ka]]susaṃmitaṃ M

24d mastake] N; matsyake M

25b kumbhasthaṃ] N; kumbha[-] M

25c kīlakāṃ] em.; kīlakā NM • maṣṭilāṃ N; muṣṭikā M

26c ālaṃkṛtān vitān] M; ālakṛtā[[m]]n vitān N

26d gr̥hyatri] N; gr̥hyātr M

29d śāstravit] N; saṃbhavit M

30a śaṅkuṃ] N; śaṅku M

30c bhūmyāṃ] N; bhūmyā M

- 81.31 viśantu te talaṃ nāgā lokapālāś ca kāmadāḥ
tiṣṭhantu te gṛhe hy asminn āyurbalakaraḥ sadā
- 81.32 yatra sādharmaṇo manthro hy udayaḥ praṇavo 'thavā
saṃsthāpya tena mantreṇa śaṅkuṃ paraśum āharet
- 81.33 praharantu tathā cāṣṭau pradadyāc chaṅkuṃ mastake
yadi naḥ susthitaḥ kīla aṣṭau praharaṇe punaḥ
- 81.34 kīlake hanyamāne tu nimittāny upalakṣayet
godvijāś ca rathānāgā nṛkanyāś ca varas triyaḥ
- 81.35 śaṅkhadundubhinirghoṣo vaṃśagītaravas tathā
kīle saṃtāḍyamāne tu yady etān upalakṣayet
- 81.36 sadārasutabhṛtyaiś ca nandate sarvadā gṛhī
nimittān śobhanān dṛṣṭvā tasmāc chaṅkuṃ niveśayet
- 81.37 nairṛtyāṃ ca tato gatvā śaṅkuṃ saṃsthāpayed budhaḥ
vāvyāṃ ca tathaiśānyāṃ śaṅkuṃ ārādhayet kramāt
- 81.38 digvidikṣu tataḥ kṛtvā kṣetraṃ sūtreṇa sammitām
gatvā puṣpādibhiḥ pūjākīlakāṃ susamāṃ sthirām

Mf56v

Ω = NM(→W)

N is illegible at 38ab

- 31a talaṃ] N; talā M 31b kāmadāḥ] em.; kāmadā NM
31d karāḥ] em.; karās M; karas N 32a manthro] N; mantre M
32b udayaḥ] N; udaya M 32d āharet] N; āhare M
33a praharantu] N; praharāntu M 33b chaṅkuṃ] em.; chaṅku NM
33c naḥ] N; nas M 33d praharaṇe] em.; praharanen N; praharāhana M
34b nimittāny] N; nimittān M 34d nṛkanyāś] N; nṛpakanyā M
35a śaṅkha] M; śaṅku N 35c saṃtāḍyamāne] M; saṃtāḍamāne N
36b nandate] N; nandakai M • sarvadā] N; sarvvato M
36c nimittān śobhanān] N; nimittāsobhanā M
37b saṃsthāpayed] M; saṃsthāpyayed N 37c tathaiśānyāṃ] N; tathaiśānyā M
37d ārādhayet kramāt] M; [*****] N 38c gatvā puṣpādibhiḥ] em.;
gatvāpuṣpādibhi M; [****]dibhiḥ N 38d susamāṃ] N; susamā M

- 81.39 śaṅkuṃ tathā tu sūtreṇa tataḥ sūtraṃ prasārayet
nītvā pradakṣiṇenaiva śaṅkuṃ dviguṇaveṣṭitam Wf62v
- 81.40 kṛtvā sūtreṇa śāstrajñāś caturaśraṃ samantataḥ
āgneyādiṣu kīleṣu balim dadyāt krameṇa tu Nf85r
- 81.41 āgneyyāṃ sammukho bhūtvā balimantreṇa dāpayet
ūṃ agnibhyo 'tha sarvebhyo ye cānye tatsamāśritāḥ
- 81.42 balim tebhyaḥ prayacchāmi sarve gṛhyaṃ tu mantritam
svāhākārāntasamyuktaṃ puṇyam odanam uttamam
- 81.43 tato gatvā tu nairṛtyāṃ nairṛtyābhimukhaḥ sthitaḥ
nairṛtyādhipatiś caiva nairṛtyāṃ ye ca rākṣasāḥ
- 81.44 balim tebhyaḥ prayacchāmi sarve gṛhyaṃ tu mantritam
vāyaviṃ tu diśāṃ gatvā vāyavyābhimukhaḥ sthitaḥ
- 81.45 ūṃ namo nāgarājebhyo ye cānye tatsamāśritāḥ
balim tebhyaḥ prayacchāmi gṛhyaṃ tu puṇyam odanam Mf57r
- 81.46 īśānīm tu diśāṃ gatvā īśānyābhimukhaḥ sthitaḥ
ūṃ ṛdrebhyaś ca sarvebhyo ye cānye tatsamāśritāḥ
- 81.47 balim tebhyaḥ prayacchāmi gṛhyaṃ tu sumanotsukāḥ
evaṃ samtarpitā devā bhavanti karmasiddhidāḥ
- iti sūtrapātalakṣaṇaekāśītipāṭalaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

- 39d śaṅkuṃ] N; śaṅku M 40d tu] M; tuḥ N 41a bhūtvā] N; dbhūtvā M
41d samāśritāḥ] N; samāśṛtaḥ M 42a tebhyaḥ] N; tebhya M
• prayacchāmi] M; prayatsāmi] N; 42c kārānta] N; kārantu M
42d puṇyam] M; puṇyāṃ N 43a nairṛtyāṃ] N; [---] M 43b mukhaḥ] M; mukha{ḥ} N
43d nairṛtyāṃ] N; nairṛtyā M 44a prayacchāmi] em.; prayatsāmi NM
44b gṛyaṃ tu] em.; gṛhyantu N; gṛhyanti M 44c diśāṃ] em.; diśāṃ N; diśā M
44d mukhaḥ] N; mukha M 45b samāśritāḥ] N; samāśṛtaḥ M 46a īśānīm] N; īśānī M
46b mukhaḥ] M; mukha N 46d cānye tatsamāśritāḥ] N; vātatsamāstathā M
47a prayacchāmi] N; prayatsāmi M 47b gṛyaṃ tu] N; gṛhyanti M
• sumanotsukāḥ] N; sumanotsukā M 47d siddhidāḥ] N; siddhidā M after 47 iti
sūtrapātalakṣaṇaekāśītipāṭalaḥ] em.; itisūtrapātalakṣaṇapaṭalaḥ N; itisūtrapātalakṣaṇaekāśītipāṭala
M